

What is the effect of an open access makerspace on the development of its community? Literature Review

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Abstract

Open-access makerspaces are popping up everywhere. They claim to provide their communities an essential portal to a world of opportunities. How do we know if they achieve this? This review summarises the available literature on the effect of open-access makerspaces on the communities in which they exist, and discusses potential measures of those effects.

The open-access makerspace is something of a new concept that doesn't fit neatly into traditional economic models. A makerspace offers benefits not easily tested by conventional outcomes-based measures. These problems pose a challenge for those seeking support for a makerspace, and for funders who may have difficulty understanding the role of today's makerspace or are reticent about investing in a relatively untested concept.

There is scant quantitative information available describing the effect of an open-access makerspace. This literature review focuses on largely qualitative information. It casts a wide net across seminal books on the Maker Movement, surveys, criticism, and social innovation writing to pull answers together.

A well supported open-access makerspace can provide advantages to all members of a community by providing access to a recent convergence of technologies in a collaborative setting. The effect of a makerspace on the development of its community can and should be measured.

It is hoped that this review will be a tool for those starting or supporting an open-access makerspace.

Keywords

Makerspace, open access, development, community, economic

"If you thought the web was big, I think this [the new maker revolution] is going to be bigger." — Chris Anderson, *Wired* magazine editor-in-chief, 2001-12

1 Introduction

Open access makerspaces are collaborative work spaces equipped with both digital and traditional tools and expertise for making almost anything. The modern makerspace is driven by the rise of digital tools like 3D printers, laser cutters, CNC mills, plotters and associated internet resources. Makerspaces exist in many countries and assume many names (eg: Fab Lab, Techshop, MakeCreate). *Open access* makerspaces serve and reflect their local communities. They provide individuals, groups, schools and businesses opportunities for tinkering, prototyping and small manufacturing, as well as instructional classes for using the available tools.

The *Maker Movement* is a social movement with an artisan spirit. Maker culture emphasizes learning-through-doing (active learning) in a social environment. Maker culture embodies informal, networked, peer-led, and shared learning motivated by fun and self-fulfillment. Maker culture encourages novel

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applications of technologies, and the exploration of intersections between traditionally separate domains (Wikipedia).

Open source is generally a software term. It refers to free access to a product's design or blueprint, the ability to modify it, and universal redistribution (Wikipedia).

Some educational institutions, companies or government entities have private makerspace facilities to serve their internal pursuits. However, this review is focused on those makerspaces set up to empower those who are *excluded* from institutional access. Note that this audience might not be the usual picture of “excluded” — it can include schools, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), working or retired professionals, parents, children, artists as well as marginalised citizens.

The purpose of this review is to investigate the practical, economic and social components of an open access makerspace in order to understand its potential role in the collective empowerment and development of its community, and to provide ideas for authentic measures of makerspace success.

This review begins with a description of the opportunities offered by technology resources for makers at this moment in time, and who might benefit the most from these conditions.

Social enterprise is the application of commercial strategies to maximize improvements in human and environmental wellbeing. This is discussed (with case studies of community engagement and resilience) for its close relationship to the function of makerspaces.

Kaupapa Māori refers to a Māori philosophical approach to the world. It incorporates the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values of Māori society. Māori are the indigenous people of New Zealand.

This review will then focus on three areas: how makerspaces and like-minded entities could develop in tandem; how purposeful making projects allow the self-development of marginalised citizens; and what are the most useful measuring and reporting tools for makerspaces and their funders. Although little (or no) existing literature has investigated kaupapa Māori in makerspaces, this review touches on the whakarara (parallels) and potential of a Māori world view woven into a collaborative makerspace.

Two comprehensive books are referred to: *The Maker Movement Manifesto* by Mark Hatch, former CEO of Techshop — a network of large-scale US and internationally franchised makerspaces started in 2006; and *Makers: The New Industrial Revolution* by Chris Anderson — former editor in chief of Wired magazine, now CEO of 3D Robotics.

Three studies are reviewed and provide closer focus: *Making Community: The Wider Role of Makerspaces in Public Life* (Taylor, Hurley, Connolly (UK), 2016); *Makerspaces and Local Economic Development* (van Holm (US), 2017); and *Equitably-consequential making by, for and with marginalized youth* (Tan, Calabrese Barton, Shin, Turner (US), 2016).

A 2013 article by NZ social entrepreneur Vivian Hutchinson discussing “creativity for the common good” and three chapters from his 2012 book *How Communities Heal* are discussed; and a critical review of the Maker Movement by Evgeny Morozov (New Yorker, 2014) provides counterpoint. Minor sources are also cited.

“Instances of access to the tools of R&D outside of institutional direction are exceedingly rare. Why?...The tools of the industrial revolution have been exceedingly expensive, hard to use and of limited power — until now.” Now they are “cheap, easy to use, and powerful, yet we have not made any changes to how we organise access to these tools. Those countries that change the fastest in this regard will have serious competitive advantage.” — Mark Hatch, former CEO of TechShop

2 What’s so special about today’s opportunities for makers?

To provide context, Mark Hatch (2014) and Chris Anderson (2014) plot a brief history of the global making economy: The industrial revolution (beginning around 1760) saw the rise of expensive mass manufacturing machines and the corresponding decline of accessible people-powered tools. The result was a socio-economic split — well resourced entrepreneurs built and controlled manufacturing infrastructure while average craftspeople lost control of the tools of production and so became factory labourers.

Fast forward to late 20th century China. The global manufacturing economy is disrupted through cheap labour and a corresponding reduction in the cost of tools. But innovation in the physical economy remains inaccessible to the masses, and available only to the privileged few.

Fast forward to today. The rise of computing power and the internet has enabled exponential growth of the global *digital economy*. Anderson (2014) and Hatch (2014) argue that today we are at the cusp of “the new industrial revolution” — a much bigger, internet-enabled *physical economy*, sparked by democratised access to 21st century technology. The opportunity for any citizen to participate in the global economy is enabled by four converging technologies: 1. The cost of tools and materials has reduced. 2. Barriers to knowledge and skill have dropped. 3. Crowdfunding mechanisms have emerged. 4. Access to markets has globalised.

Today, a range of sophisticated 2D and 3D design software with easy user interfaces is freely available to use on any device with internet access. Accompanying this are libraries of freely shared designs for output on 3D printers, laser cutters, computer-controlled mills and plotters. Anyone can find a design, modify it, print it, and repeat the process with further iterations for the relatively small price of their own time and materials. Microcontrollers are tiny computers embedded in many common tools and appliances at home and work. They can be augmented with sensors, speakers, lights, etc. Microcontroller technology is open source. This makes the hardware inexpensive and easy to tinker with because online libraries of useful microcontroller code are freely shared by the global community. Inside a makerspace this kind of material resource can be combined with access to digital and traditional fabrication tools in a knowledge-sharing setting.

Hatch questions the implications of not engaging with this convergence, arguing that The Maker Movement is creating an in-the-know pool of people with infinite possibilities at their fingertips. He asks, shouldn't communities seize this opportunity to build local knowledge and community resilience? Further, do makerspaces provide conditions for growing a prototype idea into a marketable product? It might be smarter to ask where and how marketable products are born and supported in the absence of a makerspace.

Traditional avenues for taking an innovation to market have been limited to: a manufacturer using their in-house resources to prototype, produce and market their ideas; a company or entrepreneur commissioning a prototype financed by loans and mortgages; or outside “angel” investors funding an idea they think will make money. Funding from angel investors and business accelerators come with extremely high barriers. Pitched ideas must appeal to a finite panel of judges who may not be in the product's target market. For a pitch to be successful in this setting, a fully conceived product, team, business plan, market testing and exit plan must be presented (“Pitching Masterclass”, Reitel 2017). Today 85-90% of this type of investment goes to digital startups, perhaps due to a lack of local infrastructure to support prototyping for physical startups. Most potential entrepreneurs will not reach or risk any of these thresholds.

Crowdfunding, however, offers an alternative funding method for developing products. Anderson (2014) and Hatch (2014) describe crowdfunding as an opportunity for the maker community to pursue entrepreneurialism without great individual cost. Posting a pitch to a crowdfunding site (eg Kickstarter, Indiegogo or PledgeMe) directly connects an innovator to a potential global market. Morozov (2014) points out “if you need to raise money on Kickstarter it helps to have fifty thousand Twitter followers, not fifty.” The crowdfunding process does triple duty. First it tests market approval by pre-selling (or failing to pre-sell) to enough contributors to meet a stated funding target. “Getting that information...is invaluable and ‘de-risks’ one of the most hard-to-access factors in any startup.” (Anderson 2014). Second, success via crowdfunding provides a clear cut signal for the innovation to be taken to market, and third, it becomes a channel for end-user feedback. “Kickstarter turns customers into a community” (Anderson 2014).

Crowdfunding is an example of digital and collaborative tools enabling physical making. The market for a product is no longer confined by geography or a limited local population (Hatch 2014). Crowdfunding uncovers markets that were previously impossible to find. In Anderson's 2009 book he coined the phrase “the long tail”, an economic trend powered by network effects. Its outcome is more producers making fewer products each, for more niche markets. “The great opportunity in the new Maker Movement is the ability to be both small and global. Both artisanal and innovative. Both high-tech and low-cost...creating

the sort of products that the world wants but doesn't know it yet, because those products don't fit neatly into the mass economics of the old model." (Anderson 2014).

"I still can't help but see a gulf the size of the Pacific Ocean being allowed to open up before our eyes. And I can't help but believe that addressing this issue is perhaps the most important challenge facing us if we want to innovate for good...for all, and not just for some." — Derek Handley, co-creator Hyperfactory, The B Team, Aera VC

3 Who might benefit from these opportunities in a way that hasn't been available before now?

"At \$100,000 invention isn't done. At \$1,000 it is!" (Hatch 2014).

A survey of the effect of makerspaces on local economic development in Georgia, USA found that established businesses benefit from makerspace interactions more quickly than budding entrepreneurs starting from zero (van Holm 2017). Hatch (2014) describes makerspace access for businesses who otherwise lack the resources to test an idea *causing* innovation as well as driving down the cost. A typical company spends 3-5% on research, so by definition most of its employees are not working on innovation. Their energy is spent on today's products, not tomorrow's. Makerspaces provide the opportunity to accelerate innovation through *outsourcing* (buying making expertise) and *insourcing* (hiring makerspace-based labour). He describes makerspaces enabling local on-demand manufacturing, troubleshooting and upgrading with replacement parts, avoiding inventory cost and distribution time. The survey also revealed that makerspaces can provide workforce training for local businesses and increase employee retention with the lure of access.

Hatch (2014) provides a training/retention example: The carmaker Ford partnered with Techshop to open a makerspace, and provided membership as an employee reward linked to their submission of innovation ideas. It measured a 50% increase in the quantity and quality of new ideas flowing into the company by its own people. A Ford team who moved into the makerspace developed Open XC, a digital open source platform that allows anyone to retrieve Ford vehicle sensor data. Speculating, someone in that makerspace might have followed this development and used the sensor data in their own project.

"The biggest transformation is not in the way things are done, but in who's doing it". (Anderson 2014). Anderson and urban studies theorist Richard Florida (2014) define "who's doing it" as the "creative class" — engineers, artists, lawyers, programmers, designers and others with the propensity to create. Hatch (2014) calls this "the largest untapped resource on the planet" and would like to see this community connected with makerspaces. He contends that when disposable income, disposable time, and easy access to tools come together, innovation "becomes a personal decision" with no authority figure to say 'this is a bad idea, stop doing it', nor threat of bankruptcy if it fails. Hatch (2014) and van Holm (2017) cite "lifestyle businesses" arising from these conditions. They might be short-life, small or social enterprises that provide a short-term income for founders.

Taylor et al., (2016), Tan et al., (2016) and van Holm (2017) highlight credible UK and US research which shows that underrepresented communities with a curiosity to create — but which have fallen through the cracks — benefit when they are given access to maker-type activities. Taylor et al. (2016) targeted their UK research at disabled people using makerspaces. They describe digital technology removing physical disabilities to making, and cite the completion of commissioned work by the disabled becoming sources of wellbeing, engagement and self-sufficiency. This survey in particular noted the problem of a lack of funding, causing a discrepancy between the potential versus actual impact of a makerspace on its community.

In his study, van Holm (2017) noted no makerspace in the US state of Georgia (of nine surveyed) offered structured classes through schools, though several offered holiday programmes. Today, school curricula are being re-conceived with project-based, cross-disciplinary learning as core principles. Schools at the front of this wave are acting with urgency to expose their students to 21st century learning through hands-on experience, but up-grading traditional school technology departments with 3D printing, laser cutting or robotics equipment is prohibitively expensive and requires expertise to maintain. An offsite makerspace

might be well equipped, but there are transportation, timetable and cost barriers, with off-site learning treated as an extra, and costs passed to students (Hatch 2014). Makerspace tools are appearing in schools — the challenge is to use these for meaningful learning, and avoid underused equipment languishing in a corner. Providing teacher professional development or teaching whole classes at school may be the most accessible way for makerspaces to develop schools capability in this territory.

4 What role do makerspaces have in the social enterprise and community development spectrum?

Vivian Hutchinson (2013), a founding member of The NZ Social Entrepreneur Fellowship, describes our economy as “ruled by the appetites of the consumer and a culture of commerce that has a vested interest in keeping those appetites unsatisfied.” He advocates for “Entrepreneurship for the Common Good” (2012), arguing for the redefinition of development — beyond business as usual — toward social capital, by deploying citizen-centred “creativity for the common good”. He uses the current New Zealand housing affordability problem to illustrate a contrast: corporate banks make money on mortgages and brand themselves by sponsoring major community resources, but have no strategy for affordable housing. By contrast, the NZ Housing Foundation is a charitable trust which is developing housing for low-income and disadvantaged households and co-funding shared home ownership.

Hutchinson (2013) criticises today’s community development sector as a form of event management. “Too many of our social services are just organising problems, rather than solving or healing them.” He calls for a “switch in thinking” to make resources available for the greater challenge of social change, to “permanently alter the perceptions, behaviours and structures that are creating the problems in the first place.”

He Iwi Kotahi Tatou Trust demonstrate the switch Hutchinson advocates for. They established a recording studio and multimedia film production facility in Moerewa, Northland, and have run Community Korero to find alternatives for the high imprisonment of Māori. “Young people are faced with an education system that is failing them, and a job market that has no use for them.” Specifically addressing their Māori community, the group is driven by “the healing power that comes with unleashing the creative spirit”. The group suffered a year-long period of unsustainability, crucially learning “what really matters is rebuilding the whole community infrastructure, rather than just creating a host of services.” (Chapter 15 “Making the What”; Hutchinson 2012). This is a distinction rooted in kaupapa Māori, and can be related to the function of makerspaces.

Gathering for informal connectivity and serendipitous exchange of ideas is core to makerspace culture (Hatch 2014). Taylor et al. (2016) refer to makerspaces as *third places* — a term attributed to American urban sociologist Ray Oldenburg, who writes about the importance of informal public gathering places for a functioning civil society, democracy, and civic engagement. “Social spaces separate from the home and workplace that play a critical role in public life”.

5 How can makerspaces work with like-minded organisations?

To grow a vibrant creative culture within a community requires purpose, support, design and infrastructure (Anderson 2014, Hatch 2014, Hutchinson 2012, 2013, Taylor et al. 2016, van Holm 2017). Is this what makerspaces can develop with like-minded entities?

Most makerspaces belong to regional, national or global networks (eg Fab Lab) to share ideas, progress and problems for the support and development of each other. Well resourced makerspaces are significantly more successful at maintaining services and connectivity than lean ones, who arguably need more support (Taylor et al. 2016).

Public libraries around the world have extended into digitally-enabled making, using their current resources to offer community courses in software and coding, and advocating for new resources to add “community makerspace” to their function. “Makerspace values strongly echo the core mission of public libraries of providing equal access to knowledge resources. Access to digital fabrication is now seen as a

natural progression for libraries, beyond their existing provision of basic computers and internet access. The existence of makerspaces in libraries also places them in a culture that has traditionally served as an open access hub of community activity and information. “They are both a community space and a space for communities, and consequently respond to local factors” (Taylor et al., 2016).

Businesses have a long tradition of supporting community initiatives. If makerspaces can form relationships with local companies beyond simply transactional, they begin to develop a sustainable collaborative ecosystem (Hatch 2014). Opportunities for those companies might include supporting makerspace access for local schools (van Holm 2017) or workforce incentives (Hatch 2014).

Makerspaces operated by tertiary institutions report positive outcomes, but are generally available only to staff and students of technical courses (Weinmann n.d.). Hatch (2014) views this as a wasted opportunity for cross-discipline learning or chances for creative collaboration. Further, grant-funded equipment is often tied to a specific project which reserves the use of those tools for that project, rather than a more open-ended purpose. Another barrier is that once students are outside the institution, access to the makerspace is cut off. This leaves two options for the graduate or ex-student: either buy your own equipment or work for a company, using the company’s tools predominantly to deliver the company’s projects (Hatch 2014). An open access makerspace provides the opportunity for graduates to continue their development and pursuits.

A novel example of tertiary education makerspace access is Stanford University’s *d.school* (d.school.stanford.edu), a series of classes available to any graduate student. Participants are mixed into teams, given real-world projects and access to an onsite makerspace. Hatch (2014) cites Driptech, a company which began in a *d.school* course called “Entrepreneurial Design for Extreme Affordability”. The team devised a low-cost drip irrigation solution for small-plot and subsistence farmers. When the Stanford course finished the company still needed a makerspace. The local Techshop provided this.

Tertiary institutions want to demonstrate innovation but at the same time require income streams. Hatch’s (2014) view is that enabling and encouraging maker-access to more students — both during their courses and afterward — will produce more innovation, more income and play a significant part in the overall start-up economy. His forecast is for makerspaces to serve universities the way their libraries, medical clinics and gyms do — as a cross-curricular resource for the entire entity. Further, tertiary institutions can open up far greater leverage on their research grants by sharing facilities with their community. There is an opportunity for the funding world to encourage collaboration by tying funds to outcomes like community access in order to unlock unknown potential (Hutchinson 2012).

Traditional education isn’t for everyone, including many academically capable high school leavers. In the US and New Zealand most high school leavers don’t finish a formal tertiary qualification (Hatch 2014, Hutchinson 2012, 2013). Apart from scheduled classes, makerspace access is usually self-directed, but there are some formal education options. For example Fab Academy is a model of distributed learning offered via the Fab Lab network. Students learn part time for five months in local peer workgroups with accredited mentors and tools “to make (almost) anything” (Fabacademy.org). The course brings together international and local students of any age and stage and students have open access beyond the fee paying period. Today, there are globally 100+ Fab Labs within tertiary institutions that offer this course.

“Innovation Commons” is a recently defined term for self-organising collectives of technology enthusiasts including industry, education, arts, culture and entrepreneurship entities (Allen & Potts 2016). An example of this is the project teams coalescing around Fab Lab Berlin and medical technology company Ottobock as a result of their co-creation of an Open Innovation Space — a multi-building development in a large former brewery. Fab Lab Berlin co-founder Wolf Jeschonnek states the “goal of the cooperation is to make our ecosystem for open innovation projects sustainable and to let it grow further”. Multiple products are in development or production — many cross-collaborations between students, freelancers and company staff (“Open Innovation Space,” 2018). Another example is the Innovation Commons in Erie, Pennsylvania USA. This ecosystem is anchored by the local gaming authority’s strategy for economic development and Penn State Behrend business and engineering schools, who have made their makerspace open-access with student experts on hand (“Open Innovation at Penn State”, 2016). This forms part of a bigger “Innovation District” in Erie city, designed to stimulate job creation and economic development

("Downtown Erie Innovation District", 2017). Fab Cities are similar initiatives — urban collectives with distributed manufacturing and resilience at their heart ("Fab Cities", n.d.).

6 How can makerspaces support marginalised citizens, and what effect might this have on developing kaupapa Māori?

Hatch (2014) argues for the democratising effects of makerspace access, but who might still be missing? Tan et al. (2016) reported little evidence the maker movement has had sustained success at involving a diverse audience. Implicit socio-historical narratives about *who* can be a maker influence how citizens see themselves as capable in making, or belonging in a makerspace.

Tan et al. (2016) wanted to learn the effect of a making project on young people from marginalised communities. They conducted a critical ethnography to investigate "equity-oriented making pedagogies" by inviting (largely) African American middle-schoolers into a makerspace. The study collected qualitative data over a three-year period as youths progressed and reflected on the brief, "Innovations for safety in communities". The intent was to seek "responses to basic questions of social injustice and equity as a part of — not apart from — the technical and social dimensions of their making work." Among the students' innovations were a solar powered rape-alarm jacket for teenage girls, an anti-bully app that crowd-sourced bully "hotzones", and a remote controlled childproof gate for mobility-impaired caregivers. *Expansive learning* was used, "emphasizing the importance of that which is not yet there" to allow "transformation and creation of culture". These young people were positioned not as recipients, but as partners "capable of representing themselves and others, and with important insider knowledge for doing so in powerful ways." Rather than working on a specific imposed project, the youth had free agency to define their project before creating it — *agentic creativity*. Further, by carrying out a research process and creating prototypes, the young people were empowered to "de-normalize the injustices they experience through a more informed framing of the forces that precipitate such injustices, and to craft an agentic response that can bring about positive change." An important theme emerged: the *decolonisation* of knowledge production.

The Taylor et al. (2016) study of 15 UK makerspaces and their wider role in public life identified two Northern Irish facilities located at "interface areas" where nationalist and unionist parts of the city meet, to purposefully "bring people together around shared creative activities regardless of their backgrounds." "We're moving into...having a focus on social enterprise and social innovation...if people feel that they have a future and they play a part in that future then you're offering hope and you're more likely to take the tension out of divided communities."

Vivian Hutchinson collaborates with like-minded locals in Taranaki to offer "Tu Tangata Whenua - Masterclasses for Active Citizenship" (tutamawahine.org.nz), including versions run in a Māori context "where the weaving between people can take place". The goal is to generate a foundation for resilience and regeneration. Classes are funded by local trusts and businesses. Hutchinson cites a whakatauki, "Ko te kai o te rangatira, he korero" (conversation is the food of chiefs), and acts on this. He partners with New Plymouth District Council to conduct "Community Circles...gatherings of active citizens drawn from all different sectors and activities and passions", who meet in Council Chambers, "the heart of an important civic space." There is genuine potential for developing Kaupapa Māori and socio-cultural identity in a community via these methods.

None of these actions can be token. They must be driven by a genuine reach into marginalised communities to draw those people into opportunities for agentic creativity. We might see this reach through the concept of *wairuatanga*; "the principle of cultural integration that holds all things together over time; it is as material as it is metaphysical; as contemporary as it is ancestral." (LiteracyNZ 2012). In practise, forming personal face-to-face relationships across societal divisions to connect makerspace providers with the marginalised community, providing opportunities for the marginalised to define their own problems before solving them, and allowing time for mutual trust to grow.

7 What legitimate tools exist to measure and report the benefits and risks of a makerspace?

“As social innovators and entrepreneurs look for the resources to launch their new ideas, they inevitably find their way to investors, grant-makers, government departments, corporate sponsors or philanthropic individuals... who will be asking much the same questions:

- How will we know we are getting value for money?
- How do you plan to determine the value of what’s being done?
- How will you measure the impact of your ideas and projects?”

(Chapter 13, *Measuring the Maybe*; Hutchinson, 2012).

Books and articles examining the makerspace effect are heavy with anecdotal evidence and qualitative data. This may be because resources for quantitative studies of makerspaces are lacking. It might also imply that its most valuable effects are unable to be measured quantitatively (Anderson 2104, Hatch 2014, Hutchinson 2013, Tan et al. 2016, Taylor et al. 2016). If numbers alone are not the best measure (eg attendance, income vs outgoings), it would be useful for funders to have an alternative way to ascertain a makerspace’s role in supporting, hatching or attracting local businesses, building community resilience, providing productive social connection, providing formal education, or incidental learning that occurs outside of formal education.

Funders are comfortable supporting finite projects with measurable value for money. Fund seekers must conform to this, presenting their initiatives as tidy linear projects with projected numbers and closed-circuit outcomes by a finish date. There are aspects of a makerspace that are quantifiable, but their intrinsic value can’t be counted or pre-ordained — it’s experimentation, it’s qualitative, and it’s ongoing. Hutchinson (2013) identifies this gap between what is reported to funders and what authentic good is occurring, and advocates for a redefinition of success. He challenges funders to better understand social innovation and create new measures. A “very real power struggle [is] going on between the social innovations and the status quo” with the “inappropriate use of business paradigms in a complex social context, and the anxious drive to reduce results into simplistic commercial terminology in order to gain support from funders.”

Hutchinson (2013) also suggests more pragmatism is required from social enterprises to “measure the maybe”. By focusing on linear outcomes like “in with an idea, out with a start-up business” (eg “Zero to Maker”, David Lang, 2013), makerspaces are encouraging narrow success criteria because this is just one among many reportable positive effects of an open access makerspace. The very definition of a start-up varies, and a makerspace may be one of several significant services contributing to a successful start-up. Van Holm (2017) concluded from his Georgia survey that “in part because of their recent development and small memberships, makerspaces are unlikely to launch many entrepreneurs into their communities anytime soon.”

Hatch (2014) suggests the independence of foundations and trusts (in contrast to government) is an opportunity for them to define new, innovative “proof points” to measure makerspace effectiveness. His manifesto is laden with qualitative, anecdotal examples of ideas executed, each startlingly unique in trajectory and definition of success, but all requiring crucial access to a makerspace to progress. Data can measure the number of visits or the rate of tool use within a makerspace, but this is a small part of the picture. No quantitative measure could capture the successes Hatch describes, particularly the value of serendipitous meeting and collaboration.

Martin Fisher of Kickstart International calls on both social entrepreneurs and funders to raise their game on assessing impact. He suggests four alternative questions to ask, to assess the probability of real, large-scale, lasting change:

Does the project have measurable and proven impacts? (List them, with how and when they will be measured).

- [How] are the impacts cost-effective?

- [How] will the impacts be sustained?
- [How] can the model be scaled and replicated? (Hutchinson, 2012).

For example, John Stansfield of the NZ Social Entrepreneur Fellowship suggests measuring scalability not as a multiplication of products, services or outlets, but as “citizen engagement” — raising the entity’s profile within the community — telling the stories so that others decide to “give that a go too” (Hutchinson 2013).

As an alternative to traditional evaluation, *developmental evaluation* acknowledges an entity’s “emerging, unfolding, and complex journey” where “success” is a moving target. In this reflective practice, rather than external evaluation of pre-determined outcomes, the evaluator could be inside the project team providing feedback and direction, reporting stories and creating new measures. (Hutchinson attributes this idea to Michael Quinn Patton in his book “Getting to Maybe”). Later, *formative evaluations* (ways of improving) and *summative evaluations* (overall effectiveness) can be devised and deployed (Hutchinson 2013).

To bring these measurement ideas into practise, a formal document could be co-produced by makerspaces and their funders outlining agreed quantitative and qualitative measures. Quantitative measures might include the number of school bookings per term; qualitative measures might include regular site visits for funders to interact with makers and their projects. Authenticity can be achieved through this mix.

8 Conclusion

The effects of an open-access makerspace can be spread across many realms; business, education, social and cultural.

This has meant that the *value* of development offered by a makerspace is difficult to harness, but multiple qualitative examples demonstrate benefits, with infinite potential for more. While quantitative measures have tended to be on a small scale so far, there is an opportunity to formalise these measures with a view to generating robust data — perhaps a resource tailored to open-access makerspaces, and offered open source via a network such as fablabs.io.

To sustain a makerspace with open access, partnerships with like-minded entities (private or public) are often necessary and desirable, bringing additional perspectives, expertise and priorities as well as resources.

The effect of a makerspace lies in its role as a catalyst for development that might see ultimate success outside its doors, rather than acting as the sole incubator of products and people. If a community supports its own Maker Movement it is likely to generate economic development beyond makerspaces alone, and amongst an innovation commons, acting as a magnet for other innovative entities to coalesce near it and this creative cluster in turn lures people and commerce. A network of makerspaces can spread a culture of creativity, and provide niches for sub-communities (van Holm 2017).

Development is also likely through the inclusion of a creative class and marginalised citizens who are otherwise without an outlet to make their ideas real. Typical open-access characteristics like flexibility and a culture of inclusion mean widely varied interests can be catered for in makerspaces.

This literature review reveals the tremendous advantages a well supported open-access makerspace can offer its community. It also reveals that an under supported open-access makerspace is unlikely to fulfil its potential or to be sustainable. Communities which recognise the convergence of digital and physical technology, and support its combination with social, cultural, business or education activity in a shared space will have a jump on communities who don’t.

9 Addendum

9.1 Techshop evolves

Techshop, the commercial giant of makerspaces, shut down all 10 of its US locations in November 2017 citing inadequate finance. (Its international franchises continue to operate under independent ownership).

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American business magazine, Forbes: “TechShop's failure to find a sustainable business model can be explained by a combination of lack of vision and the high cost of operating its studios, from renting huge spaces in costly urban areas, to hiring experienced staff, leasing the tools and industrial strength equipment, plus paying for insurances and utilities.

...we believe that TechShop management failed to act sooner...to close or transfer unprofitable studios and actively seek enough partnerships with local ecosystems (universities, companies, cities...) to offset its operating costs.” (November 2107)

Techshop’s San Francisco makerspace is currently reopening as “Techshop 2.0” under new ownership.

9.2 Important distinction between social enterprise and an open access makerspace

A social enterprise is a for-profit commercial business with human and/or environmental well-being built into its operation. Eg: a buy-one/donate-one model or a co-working space.

An open access makerspace can’t be a social enterprise because it supports the development of local industries rather than competing for commercial work. It relies on what income can be gained from access fees and paid workshops. In this picture, sustainability means continuous grant funding and the goodwill of expert volunteers.

9.3 If it’s not a business, not a social enterprise and not a school, what is it?

To understand a truly open-access makerspace, think of a public library — an open-access information space. Public library governance provides physical space, equipment and an operating budget, which together make anyone’s access to books and services free or subsidised.

Multiple examples of library-associated makerspaces are discussed in US periodical *The Atlantic* (Deborah Fallows, March 2016). Below is an excerpt:

“Miguel Figueroa, who directs the Center for the Future of Libraries at the American Library Association, says makerspaces are part of libraries’ expanded mission to be places where people can not only consume knowledge, but create new knowledge.

The first modern library makerspace appeared about five years ago in the Fayetteville Free Library in upstate New York. Lauren Smedley, a graduate student in Library and Information Science at nearby Syracuse University, proposed the idea of bringing a 3D printer to the library. Library Director Sue Considine liked the idea and with the entire library team, built on it and created what would be the first makerspace. That was just the beginning. Today, Fayetteville’s 2,500-square-foot Fab Lab (stands for fabrication laboratory, and is a common name for makerspaces) has expanded to include a Creation Lab for teens and pre-teens, and a Little Makers space for the tiniest makers.”

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